

Atmospheric Neutrinos in DUNE

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On behalf of the DUNE collaboration

The Deep Underground Neutrino Experiment

Main features of DUNE:

- Wideband (anti)neutrino beamline with $> 2\text{ MW}$ intensity (peak flux of 1 to 4 GeV)
- Underground **Liquid Argon TPC (LArTPC) Far Detector** with ≥ 40 kton fiducial mass
- Global collaboration of > 1400 scientists and engineers

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Also observes **atmospheric neutrinos!**

DUNE's Far Detector

Far Detector uses Liquid Argon Time Projection Chamber technology:

- Fully-active tracking calorimeters
- **Low hadronic kinetic energy threshold**
 - Proton $\sim O(25 \text{ MeV})$
- Excellent **particle identification**: (e, μ , p, γ)
- **$O(10\text{ns})$ timing information** available from scintillation light \rightarrow triggering for 3D reco.

[JINST 15 T08008](#)

DUNE's Schedule

- Two Far Detector modules will operate for 2 years without any beam
- Main source of neutrinos in early DUNE will be from atmospheric
 - $O(10^5)$ atmospheric neutrinos expected in 20 years of DUNE operation

Sensitivity to Atmospheric Oscillations

Normalisation of sub-GeV up-going atmospheric neutrinos driven by δ_{CP} :

- Can reconstruct these events due to **low hadronic kinetic energy thresholds**
- Subject to nuclear effects and cross-sections systematics

Sensitivity to Atmospheric Oscillations

Matter resonance effects occur in the 2 -- 10 GeV region:

- Well within DUNE's range for reconstruction
- Require reasonable neutrino/antineutrino separation

Sensitivity requires good energy and direction resolution:

- Dedicated simulation of atmospheric MC generated to assess reconstruction performance
- Allows optimisation of reconstruction and development of new methods

Direction Resolution

Several reconstruction techniques developed:

- Using only primary leptons (like most other detectors)
- Using all final state particles (challenging to measure kinematics of all particles)
- Using all reconstructed detector hits for calorimetric direction reconstruction

Many methods tested with **~25° angular resolution at 1 GeV for CC events**:

- Promising results with improvements expected from advanced tuning and ML
- Intrinsic limitation at low-energy due to nuclear effects, e.g. FSI, Fermi motion

Energy Reconstruction

Neutrino energy is reconstructed **via sum of leptonic and hadronic energy**:

- Primarily use **calorimetric information**; Muon reconstruction uses two alternating techniques relating to scattering depending on FC/PC (See backup for more details)

Electron Neutrino

DUNE Preliminary

Fully Contained (FC) Muon Neutrino

DUNE Preliminary

Partially Contained (PC) Muon Neutrino

DUNE Preliminary

Preliminary resolution is $\sim 20\%$ for ν_e , $\sim 8\%$ for FC ν_{μ} , and $\sim 25\%$ for PC ν_{μ} , at 1 GeV neutrino energy

Flavour Identification

Good flavour identification is **critical** to sensitivity studies:

- Use Convolutional Neural Network (CNN) to classify events
- Around 90% efficiency of tagging ν_μ and ν_e CC events

Neutrino/antineutrino separation critical to aid mass hierarchy determination:

- No magnetic field; no direct separation

Statistical separation based on:

- **Muon charge tagging** (decay vs. capture)
- **Inelasticity** (fraction of hadronic energy)
- **Primary proton tagging**

Statistical Analysis

DUNE Work In Progress

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Interpolated Honda flux
GENIE v3.0.6 G18_10a cross sections
NuFit 5.2
400 kt yr exposure

— No Oscillations
— Oscillated

Event Rate

Significant development of oscillation analysis by two fitting groups; **MaCh3** and **GUNDAM**:

- Both already involved in beam analyses; making eventual beam and atm joint fits easier
- Utilising **NuOscillator** for testing Earth modelling, path-density averaging and alternative BSM models

Systematic Uncertainties

Systematic uncertainties will play vital role for success of atmospheric oscillation analysis:

- **Detector Modelling** → Building on calibration and simulation experience within ProtoDUNE
- **Atmospheric Neutrino Flux** → Incorporating model uncertainties along with extensive model-to-model differences
- **Interaction Uncertainties** → Collaborating with experts throughout the field with input from the SBN experiments
- **Earth Topology** → Incorporating freedom in Earth layer radii and mass from moment of inertia and tomography measurements

Summary

DUNE's atmospheric oscillation analysis program is progressing quickly:

- Dedicated simulations generated include dedicated reconstruction
 - Many targeted developments improving energy and direction resolution
- Two fitting groups working towards first sensitivities

Atmospheric neutrinos provided extra sensitivity to δ_{CP} , mass hierarchy, and BSM searches like NSI

- And they are the main background to non-beam BSM searches

DUNE's schedule has 2+ years of operation of the Far Detector before beam:

- Atmospheric neutrinos will be the only abundant source of neutrinos in this period

Challenges anticipated in the evaluation of systematics:

- Working with the field leaders to ensure robust modelling of detector, neutrino interaction, atmospheric flux and Earth profile systematic uncertainties

Backup Slides

Energy Reconstruction

Neutrino energy is reconstructed via sum of leptonic and hadronic energy:

- Primarily use calorimetric information; only different for muons - 2 approaches:

Momentum resolution $\sim 5\%$ for contained muons below 1 GeV:

- Ongoing studies to evaluate hadronic and full neutrino energy resolution